

DEVELOPMENT OF A READING MANIPULATIVE TO STRENGTHEN THE PHONOLOGICAL AWARENESS OF GRADE 4 LEARNERS WITH FRUSTRATION LEVEL IN READING

Twinkle Anne G. Cullamar, Alicia Z. Maghuyop

Surigao del Norte State University, Surigao City, Surigao del Norte, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11124813>

ABSTRACT

This study explores the efficacy of a reading manipulative designed to bolster phonological awareness among Grade 4 learners experiencing frustration in reading. Employing a quasi-experimental design and the ADDIE (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation) method, the researcher developed and implemented the manipulatives that aims to focus on the following competencies: (a) counting the words, syllables, or phonemes in a word, or the words in a sentence or phrase; (b) recognizing rhyming pairs of two or more syllables; and (c) putting units of language together to say a whole word. The pretest and posttest phases utilized the Phil-IRI tool for assessment. Results indicated a significant improvement in both Word Reading and Comprehension skills among participants, supported by the rejection of the null hypothesis. The observed differences in adjusted mean scores and the statistical significance of the F-tests underscored the effectiveness of the manipulative intervention. These findings suggest that tailored reading manipulatives can play a vital role in addressing phonological awareness deficits in struggling Grade 4 readers. This research contributes to the understanding of instructional interventions aimed at supporting literacy development, particularly for learners encountering challenges in reading proficiency.

Keywords: *ADDIE Model, development, manipulatives, phonological awareness, struggling readers*

INTRODUCTION

In the context of education, manipulatives are tangible teaching tools that involve learners physically and visually through the use of items like coins, blocks, puzzles, cutout paper or even markers. In addition, children must be able to employ all six components of reading comprehension—oral language, phonological awareness, phonology, vocabulary, fluency, and comprehension—in combination (Brown, 2014).

Manipulatives are widely recommended as an efficient method of instruction for a variety of learning disciplines. Through physical interaction with real representations, manipulative-based reading methodologies enable learners to learn target information (Carbonneau and Marley 2012). The use of manipulatives enables learners to investigate concrete, tactile, and abstract concepts while developing knowledge and internalizing processes and procedures, according to Learning theory psychologist, Jean Piaget.

Reading has been a dominant problem in schools. Even before the pandemic, there were 68 learners in District VII who belong to frustration level, and it has significantly increased due to the sudden change in instruction delivery. The availability of manipulatives that would address their specific needs in reading has also been undermined.

Phonological awareness, which is a reliable foundation of reading ability (Kilpatrik, 2016), was greatly hampered during the shift and it has also affected the teaching and learning process.

The researcher was prompted to determine the effectiveness of the developed reading manipulatives that would address these competencies: (a) counting the words, syllables, or phonemes in a word, or the words in a sentence or phrase; (b) recognizing rhyming pairs, word and more syllables; and (c) putting units of language together to say a whole word, and validate if it will strengthen the phonological awareness of the learners.

Learners that exhibit any of the three major learning styles might benefit from manipulatives, especially visual and kinesthetic learners. They can also benefit people who are learning English as a second language. It is incredibly beneficial for learners to be able to use manipulatives when learning the English language, such as pictures and actual examples of the words. For instance, it would be beneficial for the teacher to give photographs of shoes and/or bring in genuine shoes to help learners build their comprehension if they do not know the English word for "shoe." The use of manipulatives benefits learners who are visual and kinesthetic (tactile) (Cromer, 2018). This study was anchored on the Theory of Constructivism by Jean Piaget, which demonstrates that people learn new things by combining their thoughts and experiences. People construct their own representations of the world and incorporate new information into their prior knowledge as they experience it and reflect on it. Manipulatives are useful tools that can encourage children to reflect and reason more deeply. Such manipulatives can help

children acquire solid, integrated understandings of concepts by giving them concrete opportunities to fully comprehend.

Research Questions

The study developed a reading manipulative that aimed to strengthen the phonological awareness of Grade 4 frustration readers of District VII, Surigao City Division.

Specifically, it sought to answer to the following questions:

1. What are the learning gaps of the pupils in terms of reading profile of the learners who belong to frustration level based on Phil-IRI?
2. What reading manipulative can be developed for learners with frustration level to address learning gaps?
3. What are the characteristics of the developed reading manipulative as assessed by:
 - 3.1 teacher-respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1.1 accessibility,
 - 3.1.2 reproduction,
 - 3.1.3 durability, and
 - 3.1.4 utilization
 - 3.2 pupil-respondents in terms of:
 - 3.2.1 content,
 - 3.2.2 visual appeal, and
 - 3.3.3 usability
4. Does the developed reading manipulative strengthen the phonological awareness of the learners?

METHODOLOGY

This study used the ADDIE reading method. It stands for Analyze, Design, Develop, Implement, and Evaluate. One of the most often applied learning models is ADDIE. It is significant because it offers a tested technique for creating effective reading materials such as manipulatives.

By following the ADDIE Model, educators can effectively identify learners' needs, design tailored interventions, implement them with fidelity, and evaluate their impact, leading to more efficient and targeted instructional outcomes.

The evaluation of learners' needs, as well as the creation of reading manipulatives, are all integrated by the ADDIE model. Additionally, and perhaps most importantly, a process that produces quantifiable and specified results can be used to evaluate the developed reading manipulative.

In **Analysis** phase, the current situation in terms of the environment and knowledge gaps are examined. In this study, the advantages and disadvantages of the reading

manipulative used were being considered and how it affected the phonological awareness of the learners with frustration level in reading.

The **Design** phase was focused on designating a reading manipulative to be used in the following target competencies: (a) counting the words, syllables, or phonemes in a word, or the words in a sentence or phrase; (b) recognizing rhyming pairs of two or more syllables; and (c) putting units of language together to say a whole word.

In the **Development** phase, it is where the reading manipulative were developed considering the following characteristics: accessibility, reproduction, durability, and utilization.

The **Implementation** phase was the actual presentation of the reading manipulative, and was used in different elementary schools at District VII, Surigao City Division to strengthen the phonological awareness of learners with frustration level in reading.

The **Evaluation** phase identified the areas that need improvement, feedback and data were gathered from pre-test and post-test in control group and experimental group. Thereafter, this information determined the design, development, and implementation of the reading manipulative's subsequent iteration.

RESULTS

The evaluation of characteristics of reading manipulatives in terms of accessibility as perceived by teacher-respondents is shown in the Table below.

Table 1. Characteristics of Reading Manipulative in terms of Accessibility as Perceived by the Teacher-Respondents

Item	Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1	It is simple to use.	3.83	0.41	Strongly Agree
2	It is readily available.	3.83	0.41	Strongly Agree
3	It is placed in an area where the pupils can use it.	3.83	0.41	Strongly Agree
4	It is transportable from one area to another.	3.67	0.52	Strongly Agree
5	It can be used in other classroom instruction activities.	3.67	0.52	Strongly Agree
Average		3.77	0.41	Strongly Agree

Table 2. Characteristics of Reading Manipulative in terms of Reproduction as Perceived by the Teacher-Respondents

Item	Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1	It can be modified.	3.50	0.55	Strongly Agree
2	It does not consume time.	3.33	0.52	Strongly Agree
3	It can be developed handily.	3.67	0.52	Strongly Agree
4	It is of high quality.	3.67	0.52	Strongly Agree
5	The materials used are readily available in the classroom.	3.67	0.52	Strongly Agree
Average		3.57	0.46	Strongly Agree

Table 3. Characteristics of Reading Manipulative in terms of Durability as Perceived by the Teacher-Respondents

Item	Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1	It is not easily torn.	3.67	0.52	Strongly Agree
2	It resists fading quickly.	3.50	0.55	Strongly Agree
3	It can be used for a long period of time.	3.50	0.55	Strongly Agree
4	The material does not easily absorb water.	3.67	0.52	Strongly Agree
5	It is adaptive to its environment.	3.67	0.52	Strongly Agree
Average		3.60	0.38	Strongly Agree

Table 4. Characteristics of Reading Manipulative in terms of Utilization as Perceived by the Teacher-Respondents

Item	Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1	It encourages engagement in learning.	3.83	0.41	Strongly Agree
2	It contains graphics/illustrations that attract the pupils.	3.83	0.41	Strongly Agree
3	It can sustain the pupil's interest in reading.	3.83	0.41	Strongly Agree
4	It is useful to strengthen their phonological awareness.	3.67	0.52	Strongly Agree
5	It is appropriate for the pupils with frustration level in reading.	3.67	0.52	Strongly Agree
Average		3.77	0.41	Strongly Agree

Table 5. Characteristics of Reading Manipulative in terms of Content as Perceived by the Pupil-Respondents

Item	Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1	It is simple.	0.97	0.17	Yes
2	It is easy to understand.	0.93	0.26	Yes
3	It helps me develop critical thinking skills.	0.93	0.26	Yes
4	It helps in establishing values in learning.	0.90	0.31	Yes
5	It helps in mastering the competencies.	1.00	0.00	Yes
Average		0.94	0.13	Yes

Table 6. Characteristics of Reading Manipulative in terms of Visual Appeal as Perceived by the Pupil-Respondents

Item	Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1	It is engaging.	0.97	0.17	Yes
2	It is attractive.	0.97	0.17	Yes
3	It can hold the pupil's interest.	0.93	0.26	Yes
4	The images and other elements are appropriate.	0.97	0.17	Yes
5	The visual presentations are easy to understand.	0.93	0.26	Yes
Average		0.95	0.11	Yes

Table 7. Characteristics of Reading Manipulative in terms of Usability as Perceived by the Pupil-Respondents

Item	Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1	It encourages engagement in learning.	0.99	0.12	Yes
2	It contains graphics/illustrations that attract the pupils.	0.91	0.29	Yes
3	It can sustain the pupil's interest in reading.	0.93	0.26	Yes
4	It is appropriate for pupils with frustration level in reading.	0.90	0.31	Yes
5	It is useful to strengthen the pupil's phonological awareness.	0.97	0.17	Yes
Average		0.94	0.13	Yes

Table 8. Difference between Pretest-Posttest Phonological Awareness

Skill	Group	Adjusted Mean	F	p	Decision	Int'n
Word Reading	Experimental	91.57	5.31	0.024	Rejected	Significa
	Control	87.71				
Comprehension	Experimental	69.44	8.80	0.004	Rejected	Significa
	Control	54.53				

DISCUSSION

Table 1. The table presents an average value of 3.77 and a standard deviation of 0.41, indicating strong agreement among teachers regarding the accessibility of reading manipulatives. Specifically, items such as "It is simple to use," "It is readily available," and "It is placed in an area where the pupils can use it" received the highest mean value of 3.83, suggesting that teachers perceive the manipulatives as user-friendly, easily accessible, and appropriately located within the learning environment. However, items like "It is transportable from one area to another" and "It can be used in other classroom instruction activities" received slightly lower mean values of 3.67, indicating a slightly lesser degree of agreement. While still rated favorably, this suggests potential areas for improvement in enhancing the manipulatives' mobility and integration into various instructional contexts to maximize their effectiveness in promoting student engagement and participation.

Table 2. Among the items with the highest mean value of 3.67, statements such as "It can be developed handily," "It is of high quality," and "The materials used are readily available in the classroom" received strong agreement from teacher-respondents, indicating their perception of the manipulatives as easily developed, of good quality, and utilizing accessible materials, thus suitable for reproduction to meet specific instructional needs efficiently. Additionally, the statement "It can be modified" garnered a mean value of 3.50, reflecting favorable perceptions regarding the manipulatives' adaptability, essential for tailoring instructional materials.

Table 3. The results revealed that items such as "It is not easily torn," "The material does not easily absorb water," and "It is adaptive to its environment" received the highest mean value of 3.67, indicating strong agreement among teacher-respondents regarding the perception of the manipulatives as durable, resistant to wear and tear, and capable of withstanding environmental factors. This positive assessment suggests that the manipulatives were constructed with quality materials and methods, ensuring longevity and reliability in classroom use.

Table 4. The table analysis revealed that items with the highest mean value of 3.83, such as "It encourages engagement in learning," "It contains graphics/illustrations that attract the pupils," and "It can sustain the pupil's interest in reading," received strong agreement from teacher-respondents, indicating their perception of the manipulatives as highly

engaging, visually appealing, and effective in maintaining students' interest in reading activities. This positive assessment suggests that the manipulatives successfully captured students' attention and motivated them to actively participate in phonological awareness exercises, fostering meaningful learning experiences.

Table 5. Table 5 presents Grade 4 learners' responses regarding the contents of reading manipulatives. The average mean value across all characteristics was 0.94, with a standard deviation of 0.13, indicating a generally positive perception among learners. The focus on simplicity, clarity, critical thinking development, and competency mastery highlights the significance of designing engaging and meaningful content that aligns with students' learning needs and capabilities.

Table 6. It can be observed from the Table that the average mean value across all items was 0.95 with a standard deviation of 0.11, reflecting a consistent and strong agreement among Grade 4 learners regarding the visual appeal of the reading manipulatives. This means that the reading manipulatives allow engagement, attractiveness, relevance, and clarity of visual presentations which are stimulating and meaningful elements into instructional materials to enhance learning outcomes.

Table 7. This positive evaluation suggests that the manipulatives effectively motivated students to engage with phonological awareness exercises, fostering a conducive learning environment. Also, the statement "It is useful to strengthen the pupil's phonological awareness" garnered a mean value of 0.97, further indicating a favorable perception among pupil-respondents regarding the manipulatives' utility in enhancing specific skills related to phonological awareness. This characteristic aligns with the overarching goal of providing instructional materials that directly contribute to students' skill development and academic growth.

Table 8. The analysis revealed significant differences between the Experimental and Control groups in both Word Reading and Comprehension skills. The Experimental group demonstrated higher adjusted mean scores for Word Reading (91.57 compared to 87.71 for the Control group) and Comprehension (69.44 compared to 54.53 for the Control group), with F-values of 5.31 and 8.80, respectively, and corresponding p-values of 0.024 and 0.004. These results indicate a statistically significant impact of the reading manipulatives on both skills, rejecting the null hypothesis and affirming their effectiveness in improving phonological awareness among Grade 4 learners with low reading ability.

Conclusions

Based on the obtained data, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. It was identified that there were 68 learners in District VII who belong to frustration level, and it has significantly increased due to the sudden change in instruction delivery. These pupils have difficulty in identifying and sounding letters, and also rhyming words that hinders their ability to read.

2. The reading manipulatives have the following features:

A. Phono Box

The Phono Box, inspired by Elkonin boxes, is a literacy tool designed to enhance phonological awareness and phonics skills in young learners by combining visual representations of phonemes with picture cards. Through activities like graphically depicting word sounds, verbalizing them, clapping each letter sound, and writing words, learners engage in a multisensory and interactive learning experience. This approach aids in the development of phonological awareness, enabling learners to segment and combine phonemes, crucial for decoding and reading fluency. By actively manipulating indicators, examining word sounds, and relating them to pictures, students deepen their understanding of phonics principles, fostering a strong connection between sounds and symbols.

B. Rhyme Box

The Rhyme Box, inspired by Dr. Seuss's vibrant vocabulary, serves as a literacy tool to cultivate phonological awareness, and facilitate the recognition of rhyming words among young learners. Featuring sets of picture cards representing rhyming pairs, this interactive strategy prompts learners to select a card, identify the depicted word, and then search for its rhyming counterpart. Through hands-on engagement with the Rhyme Box, learners refine their phonological awareness skills, honing their ability to manipulate sounds in spoken language while enjoying an immersive learning experience. By encouraging learners to discern between words with similar ending sounds and fostering their understanding of phonetic patterns, the Rhyme Box plays a pivotal role in laying the groundwork for literacy development and supporting learners on their journey to proficiency in reading.

C. Alpha Puzzle

The Alpha Puzzle, inspired by Maria Montessori's educational philosophy, serves as a reading manipulative designed to foster early reading skills through interactive and experiential learning. Consisting of a board with recessed gaps for each letter of the alphabet and corresponding puzzle pieces made of vibrant materials, the puzzle encourages learners to explore and interact with individual letters. By manipulating the puzzle pieces and arranging them alphabetically or matching them to their designated slots on the board, learners develop fine motor skills and kinesthetic learning. Rooted in the Montessori method's emphasis on self-directed learning and the use of physical objects to grasp abstract concepts, the Alpha Puzzle provides learners with a tactile understanding of the alphabet and the correlation between letters and sounds, facilitating their literacy development in a fun and engaging manner.

3. The English language teachers strongly agree that the reading manipulatives have the characteristics of accessibility, smooth reproduction, durability, and utilization.
 4. The Grade 4 learners confirmed that the reading manipulatives have contents which address the competencies for their level, visually attractive, and usable.
 5. The reading manipulatives significantly improved the phonological awareness of the Grade 4 pupils with low reading profile.
-

Recommendations

The researchers suggest the following recommendations:

1. Tailor reading manipulatives to individual learner needs by incorporating flexibility and adaptability into their design. Recognizing that each learner may have unique areas of difficulty or preferred learning styles, customizable features in manipulatives can enhance their effectiveness in addressing specific phonological awareness deficits.
2. Enhance the multisensory nature of reading manipulatives to further engage learners and reinforce phonological concepts. Integrating auditory, visual, and tactile elements into manipulative activities can provide diverse pathways for learning and accommodate different learning preferences, thereby promoting a deeper understanding of phonological principles.
3. Implement a systematic process of ongoing assessment and refinement of reading manipulatives based on feedback from both teachers and learners. Regular evaluation of the manipulatives' effectiveness in improving phonological awareness skills can inform iterative improvements to their design and implementation, ensuring their continued relevance and efficacy in addressing the needs of Grade 4 learners with frustration levels in reading.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher undergone the following procedures in data gathering:

The researcher first asked permission by sending two request letters, the first letter will be addressed to the Dean of the Graduate School for approval and the second will be addressed to the Division Schools Superintendent asking permission to administer the research instrument to the target respondents.

After the approval, another letter of intent was made to ask permission to the School Head of the target schools to permit the researcher to conduct the test to the respondents. After the dry run, the researcher conducted a survey to the teacher using the survey questionnaire and gathered data about the Grade 4 learners with frustration

level in reading based on the teacher's data using the Phil IRI tool. The pre-test and post-test were conducted to the 68 learners as identified having difficulty in reading. They were divided into two groups, the control group and the experimental group. Thirty-eight (41) of them belong to the experimental group and undergone the test using the developed reading manipulative while the other thirty-seven (27) were in the control group who did not undergo the test.

Acknowledgments

The author extends her gratitude to the Graduate School of Surigao City State University and various reliable databases online.

REFERENCES

- Brown, Carmen Sherry. 2014. *Language and Literacy Development in the Early Years: Foundational Skills that Support Emergent Readers*. New York.
- Carbonneau, K. J., & Marley, S. C. 2012. Manipulatives. In N. M. Seel (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of the Sciences of Learning* (pp. 2092-2095). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-1428-6_249
- Cromer, Michelle. 2018. "Spinitar." January. <https://blog.spinitar.com/manipulatives-as-an-important-tool-for-kinesthetic-learning-in-k-6>.
- Kilpatrick, J., Swafford, J., & Findell, B. (Eds.). 2016. *Adding it up: Helping children learn mathematics*. Washington, DC: National Academies Press.